

Paper 30

RASPBERRY PI TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Now-a-days, computer is not only a luxury but also a necessity for every person in today's world. Raspberry pi is a credit-card sized computer aimed at providing a computer to every person in the world. Raspberry Pi is intended to provide a base on which kids can learn programming while enthusiasts can do different types of commercial programming. It serves as an efficient base due to its low cost and the number of interfaces available. The Raspberry Pi can be used instead of a personal computer, but with some limitations due to its limited processing power.

Introduction

The Raspberry Pi is a low cost, credit-card sized single board developed at United Kingdom. It was designed and manufactured by Raspberry Pi Foundation from UK with the intention of stimulating the teaching of basic computer science in school's students and every other person interested in computer hardware, programming and DIY (Do-it Yourself) projects. It

acts like a computer when plugs into a computer monitor or TV, and uses a standard keyboard and mouse.

It has been ready for public consumption since 2012 with the idea of making a low-cost educational microcomputer for students and children. The main purpose of designing the raspberry pi board is to encourage learning, experimentation and innovation for school level students. The raspberry pi board is a portable and low cost. Maximum of the raspberry pi computers is used in mobile phones. It enables people of all ages to explore computing, learn programming languages like Python and can be used for many tasks that a computer does, like browsing internet, word processing, spreadsheets and also playing video.

Hardware Specification

- Broadcom BCM2837 Arm7 Quad Core Processor powered Single Board Computer running at 900MHz
- 1GB RAM
- 40pin extended GPIO
- 4 x USB 2 ports
- 4 pole Stereo output and Composite video port
- Full size HDMI
- CSI camera port for connecting the Raspberry Pi camera
- DSI display port for connecting the Raspberry Pi touch screen display
- Micro SD port for loading your operating system and storing data
- Micro USB power source

The NOOBS installer

The Raspberry Pi package only comes with the main board and nothing else. It does not come shipped with an operating system. Operating systems are loaded on a SD card from a computer and then the SD card is inserted in the Pi which becomes the primary boot device. Installing operating system can be easy for some enthusiasts, but for some beginners working with image files of operating systems can be difficult. So the Raspberry Pi foundation made a software called NOOBS – New Out Of Box Software which eases the process of installing an operating system on the Pi. The NOOBS installer can be downloaded from the official website. A user only needs to connect a SD card with the computer and just run the setup file to install NOOBS on the SD card. Next, insert the card on the Raspberry Pi.

On booting the first time, the NOOBS interface is loaded and the user can select from a list of operating systems to install. It is much convenient to install the operating system this way.

Conclusion

Raspberry Pi is an innovative product. The sheer number of users and fan base support the fact that the device can see a great future ahead. The device can surely help anyone who really wants to lean electronics and computers. Increasing the processing power can surely help the product in the future. Also supplying a case and a proper instruction manual will improve the product. Also currently Windows operating systems are not compatible because of the ARM processor. If the processor is improved or any workaround is found to run Windows directly on the Raspberry Pi, then it can be a great step for the Pi. The Raspberry Pi is an amazing piece of hardware because of the combination of the features of a traditional computer and an embedded device.

Finally, it can be said that Raspberry Pi can be effectively used if its processing power is kept in mind. It can work as a personal computer but cannot replace it.